

STUDIES IN THE NATURE OF HYDRATED FERRIC OXIDE. PART I.
INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE AND CONCENTRATION ON
THE NATURE OF THE PRECIPITATE OBTAINED BY THE
INTERACTION OF SOLUTIONS OF FERRIC CHLORIDE
AND SODIUM HYDROXIDE

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Ferric oxides of different physical properties and chemical character have been prepared for the first time by the precipitation from ferric chloride employing different quantities of sodium hydroxide and by carrying on the precipitation at different temperatures. The variation in the properties has been ascribed to the amphoteric nature of the oxide and a mechanism to explain the behaviour of ferric hydroxide has been suggested. The hypothesis has been supported by quantitative studies on the adsorption of the various ions in the system, during the precipitation of hydrated ferric oxide. The conductometric study of the precipitation has also been made.

Two varieties of ferric oxide are well known; Tommasi in 1882 (vide Weiser, "Hydrous Oxides", 1926, p. 364) recorded the existence of yellow and brown oxides, which were regarded by him as isomers. It was noted by Davies (*loc. cit.*) that the yellow variety, prepared by the oxidation of ferrous oxide or the carbonate, was denser and the solubility of this type of oxide in acids was very little. Weiser and Milligan (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 25; 1940, 44, 1087) observe that the freshly precipitated oxide is amorphous, but on ageing it gradually transforms from α - Fe_2O_3 to β - FeOOH . The yellow β -oxide is also the product of the slow hydrolysis of ferric chloride (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 238). Thiessen and Köppen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 189, 113; 1936, 228, 57) opine that brown ferric oxide yields eight hydrates on isothermal dehydration, but their view has been challenged by Weiser and co-workers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, 43, 1104). Not much work seems to have been done on the yellow oxide, and nothing is on record regarding the preparation of both of these oxides from the same reagents. It has, however, been observed by Banerji and Ghosh (*Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, Abstracts, 1942) that hydrated ferric oxide, when allowed to age gradually, becomes insoluble in mineral acids. They also observed remarkable variation in the peptisability of the oxide by hydrochloric and other acids with age. In the present investigation we have been able to prepare hydrated ferric oxides of varying colour beginning from deep brown to yellow by regulating the temperature and the concentrations of the reactants in the reaction between ferric chloride and sodium hydroxide solutions. We have also observed that in all the cases precipitation is complete even before the theoretical quantity of alkali is added. The same phenomenon has been recorded by Britton (*Ann. Rep.*, 1943, 40, 44) who studied the precipitation of various oxides by the E. M. F. method. A similar observation has been made by Dey and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 181) during the study of the precipitation of cupric hydroxide from cupric sulphate solution when the quantity of alkali required was 14% less than the theoretical amount. We have in this study made a quantitative investigation of the precipitation of ferric hydroxide by analytical and conductometric methods.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

A solution of AnalaR ferric chloride was prepared and both iron and chlorine were estimated volumetrically and gravimetrically and were in the proportion required by the formula FeCl_3 . At the outset, to 10 c.c. of ferric chloride solution were added different quantities of a standard solution of sodium hydroxide (total volume 40 c.c.) and the quantity required for just complete precipitation was noted. After filtration the filtrate was tested and was found to be acidic when smaller volumes of alkali solution were employed. The volume of alkali solution needed to yield a just alkaline filtrate was also noted. The observations were repeated at several temperatures.

TABLE I

Ferric chloride soln. = 0.575M. Sodium hydroxide soln. = 1.9418M. Theoretically 10 c.c. of ferric chloride solution $\equiv$ 8.88 c.c. of alkali for precipitation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$.

	Volume of NaOH solution at temperature of				
	25°.	40°.	50°.	60°.	80°.
For complete precipitation	8.30 c.c.	8.30 c.c.	8.50 c.c.	8.30 c.c.	8.30 c.c.
For a neutral filtrate	9.00	9.00	9.00	8.90	8.90

The effect of dilution was studied by diluting both the solutions of ferric chloride and sodium hydroxide ten times and similar observations were repeated; the results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Ferric chloride soln. = 0.0575M. Sodium hydroxide soln. = 0.1942M. Theoretically 10 c.c. of ferric chloride solution should require 8.88 c.c. of sodium hydroxide for precipitating $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$.

	Volume of NaOH solution at temperature of		
	25°.	50°.	80°.
For complete precipitation	8.50 c.c.	8.60 c.c.	8.60 c.c.
For a neutral filtrate	9.10	9.00	8.90

We thus find that on dilution the precipitation value approximates the theoretical values, and on raising the temperature, the values undergo negligible change. It was further observed that the samples of solid precipitates were readily soluble in hydrochloric and nitric acids, when precipitated with alkalis less than the theoretical amounts. The colour of hydrated ferric oxide in all these cases were dark brown. When the amount of alkali was increased the precipitate became more and more insoluble in acids. When the alkali was in great excess, the precipitate became more yellow in colour and when 10 c.c. of alkali were employed for precipitation, the colour of the oxide was deep yellow and a fair portion of the precipitate remained undissolved in even hot and concentrated hydrochloric and nitric acids, leaving a yellow residue. This insolubility was more pronounced when the precipitation was carried out at higher temperatures.

Now to 10 c.c. of ferric chloride solution, taken in several 100 c.c. flasks kept at constant temperature, were added different volumes of alkali solution, total volume

was raised to 100 c.c. and they were maintained at constant temperature for an hour. The amount of iron, sodium and chlorine ions, and also hydrogen or hydroxyl ions in the supernatant liquid were determined accurately using a microburette, by the usual methods. Knowing the amounts of the different ions taken, the amounts of ions associated with the precipitate were calculated. The results obtained at different temperatures are recorded in the following tables.

Ferric chloride solution = 0.575M

NaOH solution = 1.9418M

Iron = 0.575 g. ions per litre

Hydroxyl = 1.9418 g. ions per litre

Chlorine = 1.725 g. ions per litre

Sodium = 1.9418 g. ions per liter

TABLE III

Temperature = 25°

Mg. ions taken.			Mg. ions available in supernatant liquid.			Mg ions associated with ppt.		
Fe.	Cl.	NaOH.	H or OH.	Cl.	Na.	Fe.	Na.	Cl.
5.75	17.25	14.56	1.84 H	6.76	—	2.15	—	10.49
5.75	17.25	15.53	0.76	5.14	—	2.00	—	12.11
5.75	17.25	16.12	0.45	15.17	16.12	Nil	Nil	1.78
5.75	17.25	16.89	0.05	15.95	16.77	„	0.12	1.30
5.75	17.25	17.28	0.07 OH	16.49	17.14	„	0.14	0.76
5.75	17.25	19.42	1.67	17.24	19.17	„	0.25	0.01

TABLE IV

Temperature = 50°.

Mg. ions taken.			Mg. ions available in supernatant liquid.			Mg. ions associated with ppt.		
Fe.	Cl.	NaOH.	H or OH.	Cl.	Na.	Fe.	Na.	Cl.
5.75	17.25	15.53	0.665 H	11.01	—	4.05	—	6.21
5.75	17.25	16.12	0.041	15.29	16.12	Nil	Nil	1.96
5.75	17.25	16.50	0.016	16.64	16.50	„	„	0.61
5.75	17.25	16.89	0.010	16.88	16.77	„	0.12	0.39
5.75	17.25	17.28	0.078 OH	17.10	17.12	„	0.16	0.15
5.75	17.25	19.42	1.598	17.13	19.04	„	0.38	0.12

TABLE V

Temperature = 80°.

Mg. ions taken.			Mg. ions available in supernatant liquid.			Mg. ions associated with ppt.		
Na.	Cl.	NaOH.	H or OH.	Cl.	Na	Fe	Na.	Cl.
5.75	17.25	15.53	0.700 H	15.45	—	0.90	—	1.80
5.75	17.25	16.12	0.214	15.09	16.12	Nil	Nil	1.16
5.75	17.25	16.50	0.011	13.89	16.50	„	„	3.36
5.75	17.25	16.89	0.009	14.07	16.75	„	0.14	3.18
5.75	17.25	17.28	0.074 OH	15.76	17.11	„	0.17	1.49
5.75	17.25	19.42	1.760	16.10	18.64	„	0.78	1.15

The precipitation was also studied by noting the electrical conductivities of the supernatant liquid in the different cases when varying proportions of ferric and alkali solutions were used. For conductometric measurements a great accuracy and precision was maintained. Instead of the cell constant, the calibration constant at different positions of the bridge wire was determined by the method of Wark (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 885), and these values were employed for the calculations.

To 5 c.c. of $M/10$ ferric chloride solution were added different volumes of $M/2$ sodium hydroxide solution, total volume kept at 10 c.c. and the precipitate allowed to settle for an hour at 30° . It was centrifuged at 2500 r.p.m. for five minutes and the electrical conductivity of the supernatant liquid was determined at 30° .

In another set, the concentration of alkali was kept constant and varying amounts of ferric chloride solution were added to it. The concentration chosen was $M/4$ for both the reactants, so that at the equivalence point $\text{Fe} : \text{OH} = 1 : 3$, the concentration of the respective constituents in both the sets was almost the same.

From the conductivity results the adjoining graph has been plotted showing the variation of specific conductivity with the increase in $\text{Fe} : \text{OH}$ ratio (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

Our results on the precipitation of hydrated ferric oxide from ferric chloride solution show that similar to the observation of Britton (*Ann. Rep.*, 1943, **40**, 43) with various hydroxides, the amount of alkali needed for complete removal of the metal from solution is always less than the theoretical amount. In all such cases there are two possible reactions, which would result to such an observation.

(1) Increased tendency of hydrolysis with increased concentration of the alkali, according to the following scheme :

The above will be more marked with increasing insolubility of the respective hydroxides and their strength as a base.

(2) Hydrolytic adsorption of the anion, Cl⁻ by the basic oxide, producing free alkali :

In the first case the formation of ferric hydroxide takes place in stages, yielding various intermediate basic compounds, which ultimately with a definite excess of alkali would result in the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. In the second case, the quantity of alkali added precipitates the equivalent quantity of ferric hydroxide, which on adsorbing chlorine ions from the system liberates an equivalent quantity of OH^- ions, which precipitate more and more of the hydroxide. Our experimental results, as recorded in Tables III, IV and V, show that when the amount of alkali is deficient, the adsorption of chloride ion is high and this goes on decreasing as the quantity of alkali added is raised.

It is interesting to observe in Tables I and II that complete precipitation occurs when the supernatant liquid is slightly acidic. We find that in all the cases quoted in the aforesaid tables, the amount of alkali needed to yield a neutral filtrate is always greater than the volume needed for complete precipitation. This observation is contradictory to the case of precipitation of cupric hydroxide as observed by us (*loc. cit.*), where the filtrate becomes alkaline with complete precipitation. It may therefore appear to be anomalous, but keeping in view that ferric hydroxide is far more insoluble than cupric hydroxide, complete precipitation occurs at a lower OH^- ion concentration, so that the filtrate may remain slightly acidic even though complete precipitation has been effected.

If we regard the precipitate to be a basic salt in accordance to equation (1), shown above, it is obvious that earlier precipitation should be favoured by dilution and also by rise of temperature, as both of these are favourable for hydrolysis. A perusal of Table I shows that the amount of alkali needed for complete precipitation is not markedly affected by rise of temperature. From Table II it will be seen that with dilution precipitation occurs with the amount of alkali approaching theoretical values.

Considering the analytical data for adsorption, as presented in Tables III, IV and V, we find that the adsorption of sodium and chlorine ions varies remarkably with the amount of alkali used for precipitation. The adsorption of chlorine in general decreases, whilst the amount of sodium associated with the precipitate increases with increasing quantities of alkali added. These observations are easily explainable, when we remember that ferric oxide has an amphoteric character and the tendency of the adsorption of ions by such oxides is always governed by the hydrogen ion concentration of the medium in which the adsorption is taking place (Dey and Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1946, 15A, 143). Naturally when the OH^- ion concentration is low, the adsorption of Cl^- ions will be more prominent, while under such circumstances Na^+ ions will not be adsorbed. Thus, we find that at 25° (vide Table III) when the medium is prominently acidic containing 0.45 mg. *M* of acid, the adsorption of chlorine is 1.78 mg. ions, whereas the adsorption of sodium is nil. Now, as the medium becomes alkaline,

containing 1.67 mg. *M* of alkali, the adsorption of chlorine falls to 0.01 mg. ions, whereas the amount of sodium associated is 0.25 mg. ions.

Increase of temperature favours the association of sodium with the precipitate, whereas the adsorption of chlorine is diminished. The latter is, however, not rigidly followed by changes in temperature, as the phenomenon of hydrolysis at higher temperatures plays an important role. The association of sodium ions with the precipitate goes on increasing steadily with rise of temperature. Thus, when 19.42 mg. *M* of alkali are added to ferric chloride solution containing 5.75 mg. ions of ferric iron, the amount of sodium associated with the precipitate is 0.25, 0.38 and 0.78 mg. ions at 25°, 50° and 80° respectively.

Ferric oxide with sodium hydroxide has a tendency to form sodium ferrite, and this will naturally be more prominent at a high temperature. Van Bemmelen in 1892 (vide Weiser, "Hydrous Oxides") prepared the yellow variety of ferric oxide by the reaction between sodium ferrite and water. We are of opinion that at higher temperatures sodium is found to be associated in larger amounts in alkaline media, as direct chemical interaction results to form some sodium ferrite.

It is interesting to point out that ferric hydroxide, obtained at higher temperature with excess of alkali, was definitely found to be of yellow colour and was highly resistant towards acids. This confirms our contention that a fair portion of the ferric hydroxide undergoes a chemical transformation to form ferric ferrite, which has lost its basic properties to be acted upon by an acid, according to the following scheme :

In equation (1) ferric hydroxide acts as a proton acceptor, *i. e.* as a base and in equation (2) it donates a proton, and behaves as an acid. The chemical interaction between the acidic and the basic properties of the hydroxide in the above manner results in the formation of Fe_2O_3 , which becomes chemically inert either as an acid or a base.

The conductometric study of the precipitation of ferric hydroxide shows that though complete precipitation of iron as hydrated oxide takes place with a little lesser amount of alkali, yet the minima of the conductometric graph occurs, when Fe : OH ratio is 1 : 3.2 when ferric chloride is added to the alkali, whilst it is 2.9 when alkali is added to ferric chloride. In neither case the minima correspond to the observed ratio for complete precipitation. We are of opinion, that this divergency of the results occurs due to the adsorption of the electrolytes present, and hence no accurate information can be obtained regarding the complete precipitation from these curves. We therefore suggest that Britton's data on the precipitation of different insoluble hydroxides using the E. M. F. method (*loc. cit.*) is also beset with similar difficulties and hence fails to convey a true idea of the conditions of precipitation.